

NATURE ITSELF IS A PHYSICIAN

Usmanova Marjona Botirali qizi

Cultivation and processing of medicinal plants
performance training direction Phase 3 309 group

Tel: +9989888472211

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6880768>

Annotation: The main purpose of writing this article is to look at nature's wonderful medicinal plants, medicinal and medicinal products, and their benefits for the human body. it is not difficult to get.

Keywords: Herbs, plants, food, bark, roots, greens, vegetables, medicinal plants.

The wonder of nature is that all the plants that grow in it, and the plants themselves, are the cure for all living things. We can see how fruits, vegetables, greens and all green plants that grow in it are healing for living cells and the human body. Of all the important medicinal plants in nature, they are widely used in medicine, disease prevention, food, perfumes and cosmetics to treat people and animals. It is estimated that there are 10,000 to 12,000 species of medicinal plants in the world. The chemical and pharmacological properties of more than 1,000 plant species have been studied. There are more than 700 species of medicinal plants in Uzbekistan. Of these, about 120 species of plants that grow naturally and are cultivated are used in scientific and folk medicine. At present, about 40-47% of medicines used in medicine are derived from plant raw materials. Plants are living natural chemical laboratories with complex structures capable of creating complex organic substances or compounds from simple inorganic substances. Dried herbs, buds, roots, rhizomes, rhizomes, bulbs, bark, leaves, flowers, buds, fruits (seeds), seeds, sap, syrup, stone, essential oil and others are used as medicinal plants. There are two classifications of medicinal plants: 1) depending on the content of active substances - alkaloids, glycosides, essential oils, vitamins, etc., 2) depending on the pharmacological properties - sedative, analgesic, hypnotic, cardiovascular, central nervous system stimulant. , lowering blood pressure, etc.

The active ingredients of medicinal plants are alkaloids, various glycosides (anthraglycosides, cardiac glycosides, saponins, etc.), flavonoids, coumarins, astringents and mucus, essential oils, vitamins, dyes, enzymes, phytoncides, polysaccharides, starch, proteins, starch. substances, fats and fatty acids and other compounds. The effects of medicinal plants on the body depend on the amount of chemical compounds they contain. These compounds accumulate in different amounts in parts of the plant. The period of high potency and quality of

the drug coincides with the beginning of their flowering and fertilization period. Medicinal substances accumulate in the buds, leaves or stems of some plants, in the flowers or fruits of some plants, and in the roots or bark of some plants. Therefore, the part of the plant that is mostly rich in biologically active substances is harvested. The roots, rhizomes, bulbs, and stems of plants are usually harvested in the late fall or early spring, when the plant is dormant. The fruits and seeds of the plant are harvested when ripe, as they are rich in medicinal substances at this time. Freshly harvested medicinal plant products are moist (up to 85% in the surface organs and up to 45% in the roots). If this moisture is not removed (by drying), the plant will rot, the drugs will break down and become unusable.

Medicinal herbs have been used to treat diseases since ancient times. Some 3,000 to 4,000 years ago, works on medicinal plants were written in India, China, and ancient Egypt. In the East, especially in Central Asian folk medicine, the use of medicinal plants has a long tradition. Abu Ali Ibn Sina's Al-Qanun on the use of medicinal plants for medicinal purposes provides information on the medicinal properties of about 476 plants and their methods of use. Nowadays, the variety of medicinal plants has increased, and folk medicine has enriched it with medicinal plants. More than medicinal plants, pomegranate, bitter melon, almond, dogwood, medicinal rose, walnut, jaggery, dandelion, incense, rose hips, oranges, pistachio tree, measles, mumps, and others. Pachycarpine is used in the treatment of acne, psoralen is used in the treatment of leprosy, garmin in incense, anabazine in feverfew, galantamine in ammonia, spherophysin and other alkaloids in rhubarb. Pomegranate peel is made from worm-driving peltarin tanat and extract. Medicinal herbs are used to move and soften sputum, medicines made from jaw and lagoxilus are used to stop bleeding, pistachio buckthorn and tea leaves are used to treat stomach ailments. S.Q. The Tashkent Pharmaceutical Plant named after Islombekov produces a wide range of medicines from medicinal plants grown and cultivated in Uzbekistan. The Institute of Plant Chemistry of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan has played an important role in finding and obtaining alkaloids from medicinal plants. More than 4,000 different organs of plants have been studied at the institute to obtain alkaloids, and about 1,000 natural compounds have been isolated from them. On this basis, more than 20 valuable drugs such as cytosine, galantamine were created and introduced into medicine. That is why our people say that nature itself is a doctor, and we have given above examples of a few plants that you and I do not know, and we cannot count the rest of the medicinal plants.

We often hear in our daily lives that if we are healthy, everything else will happen by itself. It is true that a good mood, the implementation of planned activities, active pursuit of goals - all this depends on our physical and mental health. And the rest of our health is in our hands! In fact, the Uzbek table is full of various health benefits. But there are some gifts of nature that we can overlook, and you will learn below how useful it is to consume them regularly.

Why do you think the cartoon character Sailor Papay ate only spinach to gain strength? The beneficial properties of this plant have been enjoyed by our ancestors for thousands of years. Spinach fights heart disease such as vitamin K, vitamin A, manganese, iron, magnesium, calcium, phosphorus, zinc, vitamins C, E and B2, folate, protein, stomach, breast, prostate and skin cancer. Contains more than 12 different vitamins. Spinach also reduces high blood pressure, eye and vision problems, and increases bone strength.

Ginger

Originally used for culinary and medicinal purposes for thousands of years, first in China and India, and later in European countries, the root of this plant is rich in various vitamins and minerals and has the following benefits when consumed:

- ginger tea relieves nausea in pregnant women in a way that does not adversely affect the child;
- ginger tea cures sore throat, flu and colds;
- treats inflammation of the gastrointestinal tract;
- helps digestion and eliminates abdominal cramps;
- reduces pain in the knees caused by arthritis;
- helps to overcome muscle aches after sports or hard work, menstrual cramps in girls;
- warms the body and increases sexual ability.

Beet leaf

Ladies and gentlemen, did you ever put a beet leaf in it while you were cooking? The taste stays in your mouth! Most importantly, you'll be giving your family countless vitamins! Rich in vitamins A, B, C, E and vitamin K, iron, calcium, magnesium, protein and other minerals, beet leaves fight heart disease, anemia, white blood cell and lung cancer, clear the skin, improves scanning properties, strengthens bones. It is also delicious if you make a salad from well-washed beet leaves, or if you "kill" it in a pan with a tablespoon of oil.

Turnip

Even though most of us didn't like the taste as a child, cooked turnips can add a special flavor to our food. Rich in various vitamins, minerals such as iron, iodine,

phosphorus, zinc, manganese and calcium, this vegetable helps to cleanse the blood in the body, improve liver and stomach function. will give. It normalizes the heartbeat and plays an important role in the treatment of asthma and bronchial diseases. Interestingly, turnips also eliminate various odors from the body.

Note: In diseases of the liver or kidneys, it is not recommended to eat turnips raw or in large quantities. Turnips are also not recommended for people with central nervous system problems; young children should not be fed until they are 2 years old.

Bell peppers

Rich in vitamin C, this colorful vegetable boosts the body's immune system and keeps skin, gums and eyes healthy. Balances blood sugar levels; fights diseases associated with old age, asthma, heart disease and cancer.

If you regularly eat bell peppers, you will not suffer from any of the diseases associated with old age in the future! Especially our pregnant women are strongly advised to eat this vegetable often.

Pumpkin

Do you like pumpkin pie? How often do you eat pumpkin? If so, consider that you are taking good care of your health. Despite being a light diet, this vegetable, which can keep a person full for a long time, has the property of preventing prostate cancer, lung and breast cancer. Pumpkin reduces the risk of heart disease, increases the strength of cells in the body and normalizes blood sugar levels. In addition, the tryptophan substance in pumpkin, when consumed, is

converted into serotonin in the body, which has anti-fatigue and mood-boosting properties. Interestingly, pumpkin lovers can look younger for longer in life!

Carrots

As adults, we used to be told, "Eat more carrots - you'll grow taller." Interestingly, this vegetable is rich in nutrients that are important not only for growth, but also for hair, skin and eyes. In addition, the vitamins in carrots help prevent heartburn, heart disease and various cancers.

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